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Issue Tracker 2026/05
May 25, 2026

[Analysis Shows Growing Inequality in Accessing Innovative Drugs in Europe:](#) According to the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA), there is an 88% access disparity between the highest and lowest European nations, with an overall median time for availability of newly approved drugs taking 532 days. In 2025, nearly half of Europe's innovative medicines were unavailable to patients due to a lack of reimbursement or delayed approval decisions. The EFPIA also warns that global pricing reforms, such as the US Most Favoured Nation Policy, will further widen the gap.

[FDA is Advancing a New Era of Patient-Centred Care:](#) A report from the Personalized Medicine Coalition (PMC) highlights that, in 2025, personalized medicines accounted for 36% of the newly approved therapeutic molecular entities by the FDA. It included five new gene and cell-based therapies and the expedited authorization of the first CRISPR gene-editing therapy tailored for an individual patient. The PMC believes these milestones reflect a sustained shift away from one-size-fits-all medicine towards a precise, patient-centred healthcare system.

[High Count of AI Hallucinated Citations in Academic Papers and Preprints:](#) A new audit of 2.5 million academic papers and preprints has revealed that over 146 000 hallucinated citations were published in 2025 alone, with fake references disproportionately crediting already well-established authors. The study also found that the social sciences repository SSRN had the highest fake citation rate, at nearly 2%, which is about five times greater than any other major platform. However, some experts suggest this disparity may be explained by the text-heavy nature of social sciences or differences in how platforms screen and moderate AI-generated content.

[Bristol Myers Squibb \(BMS\) Enterprise-Wide AI adoption:](#) BMS has partnered with Anthropic to deploy Claude, Anthropic's AI platform, across BMS' global operations for over 30 000 employees. This collaboration moves beyond the basic usage of chatbots and aims to embed AI into day-to-day workflows to optimize manufacturing and automate clinical trial documentation. Notably, BMS aims to use Claude on proprietary research data to halve the time it takes to advance from target selection to lead molecule identification. The collaboration highlights an intensifying pharmaceutical race, as BMS joins other pharmaceutical industry giants such as Eli Lilly and Merck in securing major partnerships with top AI developers.